

GENERALIZED COMPLIANCE, A NEW TECHNIQUE FOR PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE ANALYSIS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

R. Raihan, Jon-Michael Adkins, Fazle Rabbi, Jeffrey Baker, Q. Liu, K. Reifsnider*
 Mechanical Engineering Department, University of South Carolina, Columbia, SC 29208, USA
 *K. Reifsnider (reifsnider@cec.sc.edu)

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1 Introduction

Engineered composite materials are widely used in many applications because of their unique properties and high performance, but long term property evolution in these functional material systems is still an active research area. Design and synthesis of these material systems requires a fundamental understanding of the material state changes due to the applied mechanical, thermal, and electrical fields. In the present work, we will present the recent development of a method to evaluate material integrity and durability by following the specific nature of material state change that leads to the failure of the material, using a unique experimental room-temperature, non-invasive interrogation technique.

Composite materials should be designed as a material system, by selecting the constituents, their nano- and micro-morphology, and their interfaces in such a way that their action and interaction results in the functional ability to cope with their applied environments. During a history of applied fields, changes are induced in the properties of the constituents and in their interactions with each other due to progressive micro-damage, aging, or chemical degradation. In previous work [1-6] we have shown some relationship between the local character of different morphology of heterogeneous materials and their response to applied conditions. Mechanical compliance reflects micro-damage, but it is not uniquely related to the specific nature of the damage. By contrast, generalized compliance to multiple fields could be used as a basis for specific analysis of damage and the prognosis of composite systems subjected to mechanical, electrical and/or thermally applied loads. In particular, we will show that compliance to AC electrical fields can be

interpreted in terms of the details of local damage for progressive degradation in these material systems.

2 Backgrounds for the Discussion

Liu et al. in their recent study [1-6] considered the dielectric effect of circular and elliptical embedded second phase (included) regions as a function of volume fraction, and orientation of the elliptical axis of the included phase with the vector direction of an applied electric field. For that calculation, the matrix material had negligible conductivity but significant permittivity, while the inclusion had small but finite conductivity and small permittivity (e.g. Fig.1).

Fig.1. Configurations analyzed (bottom) and stored charge in terms of “effective permittivity” (top) for a two phase heterogeneous material.

For bound charge or stored charge, a typical assumption is that the charge displacement is

proportional to the applied field, with the following notations commonly used as

$$D = \epsilon_0 \epsilon \cdot E \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon = \epsilon' + \frac{\sigma}{i\omega\epsilon_0} \quad (2)$$

where D is the charge displacement caused by the applied field E , ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum, ϵ is the relative permittivity of our heterogeneous material with real part ϵ' , ω is the frequency of harmonic changes in the applied field and σ is the real conductivity of the material. The resulting variation with increasing defect density shown in Fig. 1 is surprisingly nonlinear and generally related to the accumulation of defects caused by mechanical loading where size, shape, and orientation of cracks effects global compliance and creates local stress concentrations as they interact. To validate and apply this computational work, we choose a woven glass/epoxy composite and investigated dielectric property changes with increasing micro-cracking induced by mechanical off-axis loading.

3 Experimental Setup

Fig.2. Schematic of the Experimental setup

To perform the tensile extension of coupon specimens of the woven glass fiber reinforced epoxy coupons, strain was measured with an extensometer at the same time the electrical permittivity of the specimens was measured at a fixed frequency of 10 Hz using a Novocontrol™ unit to interpret data from the signal applied by specially designed plates fixed on opposing sides of the thickness of the specimen.

4 Results and Discussion

Dielectric spectroscopy results show that for the off axis samples, there is a generally decreasing trend in the real part of the permittivity with increasing strain as shown in Fig. 3, over a wide frequency range.

Fig.3. Real part of the electrical permittivity vs. frequency at different strain levels.

In-situ dielectric measurements for a single frequency (10 Hz) showed a nonlinear change in the real part of the permittivity of the material system which is quite similar to the results of Liu et al. where the permittivity decreased nonlinearly with increasing crack density, as shown in Fig.4. The glass/epoxy off-axis samples used here had near-zero conductivity and larger permittivity induced by micro-cracking (which has nominal properties of ambient air i.e. lower permittivity) but small conductivity because of the presence of the moisture in the air in the crack volume.

Fig.4. Real part of permittivity and load vs. strain and changing transmitted monochromatic light intensity with increasing micro-crack density.

From equation (1) and (2) it is understandable that the permittivity depends on both conductivity and the real part of the permittivity of the material. And for low frequencies, as shown in equations (1) and (2), the effect of even a small value of conductivity can be substantially large.

These changes in conductivity and permittivity in the material system are due to the non-conservative response to the applied field. So prognosis of the composite mainly depends of the properties of the fiber and matrix and the specific size, density, and orientation of the crack-density which can be predicted by analysis and directly measured by the permittivity of the system.

5 Conclusion

We have outlined a generalized compliance method for the analysis of the specific nature of the progressive damage of composite materials, in support of better design and high performance. Generalized compliance directly reflects the material state changes, so it is an effective approach to the prognosis of material behavior when future applications of fields over time and history of loading are simulated.

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